

Supplementary Material B

Details on Coding Procedure

B1. Coding Manual for Study Variables

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
Identification			
study_id	Ongoing number for each study	[Figure]	
es_id	Ongoing number for each effect size	[Figure]	
Reference			
authors	Last name of all contributing authors	[Text]	
title	Title of the study	[Text]	
pub_status	Status of publication	0 = published, 1 = unpublished	Published studies were collected through a thorough literature search in bibliographic databases, previous reviews and meta-analyses, or backward search of already included studies. Unpublished studies were collected through circular emails sent to expert groups or personal requests made to authors whose work was already included.
pub_type	Type of publication	0 = peer-reviewed journal article, 1 = conference paper,	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
		2 = book chapter, 3 = thesis/dissertation	
year	Year of publication	[Figure]	
country_author	Country where the first author's institution is located	[Text]	
country_study	Country where the study was conducted	[Text]	If not specified, country of first author's institution was used instead.
continent_study	Continent where the study was conducted	0 = Europe, 1 = North America, 2 = Asia	If not specified, continent of first author's institution was used instead.
Sample characteristics			
total_n	Entire sample size of the study	[Figure]	Number of people included in the study (after taking dropouts into account, i.e., the total <i>N</i> could differ from the initial <i>N</i> reported in the study).
age_mean	Mean age of the participants in the entire sample	[Figure]	If no mean but the range was reported, the unweighted mean was calculated and used instead (e.g., range of 40–50 years results in a mean of $(40 + 50) / 2 = 45$ years).
age_sd	Standard deviation of age in the entire sample	[Figure]	
age_range	Range of age in the entire sample	[Text]	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
n_women	Number of female participants in the entire sample	[Figure]	The number of male participants in the entire sample resulted from the difference between total_n and n_women.
control_vision	Information about participants' vision	0 = no information about vision, 1 = sample with normal/fully corrected vision	Sample with normal/fully corrected vision: sight defects (e.g., myopia, hyperopia) fully corrected, participants with color vision deficiencies (e.g., dyschromatopsia) excluded.
sample_students	Indication of whether the sample consisted of students	0 = assured student sample, 1 = potential student sample, 2 = no student sample	Assured student sample: sample consisting entirely of students at universities and/or schools. Potential student sample: sample origin unclear, or sample composed of students and non-students, with an overall mean age of about 25 years. No student sample: sample consisting entirely of non-students or composed of students and non-students with a balanced age distribution (i.e., older participants were included).
sample_compensation	Information about type and amount of compensation received by the participants	0 = no information about compensation received, 1 = compensation	Compensation refers to tangible and intangible benefits that study participants received as a reward or reimbursement for their involvement (e.g., money, gifts, course credits).

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
Moderators			
mod_device	Device the participants interact with	0 = no information about device used, 1 = computer, 2 = mobile phone, 3 = tablet	Note that the category “no information about device used” was also applied when the participants’ device could not be determined (e.g., in online settings).
mod_interface_type	Type of interface the participants interact with	0 = software, 1 = website, 2 = prototype/mock-up, 3 = element of interface	Software: broad set of functions, designed to execute specific tasks (e.g., search engines, learning platforms). Note that mobile applications were categorized as software as well. Websites: focus on displaying information, limited interaction possibilities including buttons and hyperlinks (e.g., company websites, e-commerce websites). Prototype/mock-up: low- to high-fidelity mock-up of a device or interface with limited functionality (e.g., simulated navigation system). Element of interface: frequently used element of an

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
mod_time	Time period in which the study participants interact with the interface	0 = few seconds, 1 = few minutes to an hour, 2 = few hours/days/weeks	interface that is presented on its own/outside the usual context of use (e.g., icons). Note that the category “few hours/days/weeks” encompasses long-term as well as repeated interactions with the interface.
mod_aesth_measure	Type of instrument/scale the degree of perceived aesthetics is measured with	0 = single-item scales, 1 = multi-item scales with low-level validation, 2 = multi-item scales with high-level validation, 3 = scale by Lavie & Tractinsky (2004) 4 = VisAWI, 5 = appeal items of AttrakDiff 1, 6 = other measurement	Single-item scales: scales consisting of only one item measuring the interface aesthetics, figuratively or literally anchored. Multi-item scales: scales constructed by the study’s authors, classified for coding purposes according to the quality of their validation: low-level validation (e.g., lack of cross-validation) and high-level validation (e.g., confirmatory factor analysis, construct validity, criterion validity). VisAWI: Visual Aesthetics of Websites Inventory (Moshagen & Thielsch, 2010) AttrakDiff 1: questionnaire to assess pragmatic and hedonic quality of interfaces (Hassenzahl et al., 2000), only the appeal items considered here.

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
			Other measurement: e.g., ranking scales Note that if new items were created based on standardized scales or items were adapted from standardized scales, these scales were coded as “multi-item scales.” If standardized scales were only partially used but not adapted, these scales were coded as if the entire scale had been used.
rel_aesth_high rel_aesth_low	Reliability of the aesthetics measurement scale	[Figure]	Reliability could be calculated using data from a previous study or the original study. It was reported as Cronbach’s Alpha.
mod_aesth_measure_time	Time of aesthetics assessment during the study procedure	0 = in previous study, 1 = before interaction, 2 = after interaction	In previous study: interface aesthetics assessed in a previous/preliminary study. Before interaction: interface aesthetics assessed in the original study prior to actual interaction with the interface (i.e., expected aesthetics; Lee & Koubek, 2012). After interaction: interface aesthetics assessed in the original study after interaction with the interface (i.e., experienced aesthetics; Lee & Koubek, 2012).
mod_aesth_measure_interface	Indication of whether the interface	0 = interface not	Interface not presented: participants rated interface

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	aesthetics was rated with the interface being presented	presented, 1 = interface presented	aesthetics based solely on memory. Interface presented: participants rated aesthetics while having visual access to the interface, either by viewing the interactive interface or being shown screenshots. Note that regardless of how the interface was presented during the aesthetics assessment, participants experienced the interface in an interactive state before/after the assessment, as outlined in the eligibility criteria.
mod_aesth_reference	Indication of whether the interface aesthetics is assessed collectively or individually	0 = collective assessment, 1 = individual assessment	Collective assessment: engagement with the interface version rated as more or less appealing by all participants (either in a preliminary or the original study). Individual assessment: engagement with the interface version individually rated as more or less appealing.
mod_aesth_manip_color	Change of color scheme for aesthetic manipulation	0 = no, 1 = yes	
mod_aesth_manip_texture	Change of (background) texture for aesthetic manipulation	0 = no, 1 = yes	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
mod_aesth_manip_layout	Change of layout for aesthetic manipulation	0 = no, 1 = yes	Change of layout included arrangement of elements (e.g., balance, symmetry).
mod_aesth_manip_typo	Change of typology/font for aesthetic manipulation	0 = no, 1 = yes	
mod_aesth_manip_graphics	Change in usage of graphical elements	0 = no, 1 = yes	Change in usage of graphical elements included usage of icons, animations, etc.
mod_aesth_manip_complexity	Change in complexity for aesthetic manipulation	0 = no, 1 = yes	Change in complexity included amount of detail or intricacy of an interface (or an interface element).
mod_aesth_manip_shape	Change of shape/form of elements	0 = no, 1 = yes	
mod_aesth_manip	Number of manipulated aesthetics facets	0 = manipulation of one facet, 1 = two facets, 2 = three or more facets	
mod_diff_aesth	Size of the standardized mean difference (Hedge's <i>g</i>) in perceived aesthetics between the experimental conditions	0 = very small, 1 = small, 2 = medium, 3 = large	All included studies needed to successfully manipulate the interface aesthetics, i.e., demonstrate a significant difference between the conditions. The estimation of the standardized mean difference (Hedge's <i>g</i>) between the

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
mod_task	Type of task the study participants performed	0 = free use, 1 = search task, 2 = use function	<p>conditions was based on the conventions by Cohen (1988):</p> <p>Very small mean difference between conditions: effect size of Hedge's $g < 0.2$.</p> <p>Small mean difference between conditions: effect size of Hedge's g between $0.2 \leq g \leq 0.5$.</p> <p>Medium mean difference between conditions: effect size of Hedge's g between $0.5 \leq g \leq 0.8$.</p> <p>Large mean difference between conditions: effect size of Hedge's $g \geq 0.8$.</p> <p>Free use: usage of interface without specific directions.</p> <p>Search task: task requiring participants to find a specific target and select it by clicking or tapping.</p> <p>Use function: task requiring participants to use a specific function to accomplish the task at hand, typically used in usability tests.</p> <p>Note that tasks requiring the use of a function may also include tasks involving the search for information (e.g., browsing a website for a specific piece of information).</p>

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
mod_actual_context	Context in which participants interact with the interface during the study	0 = leisure, 1 = learning	Leisure: participation during leisure time (e.g., taking part voluntarily, without or with small amount of compensation) Learning: participation in an educational setting (e.g., university, school)
mod_intended_context	Context for which the interface was developed/purpose of interface	0 = leisure, 1 = learning, 2 = work, 3 = other context	Leisure: interface mostly used during leisure time (e.g., e-commerce websites, public information websites, driving simulator, event-planning app) Learning: interface mostly used for learning purposes (e.g., educational games, e-assessment, web atlas, university website) Work: interface mostly used for working purposes (e.g., corporate websites, databases) Other contexts: e.g., healthcare/medical context (e.g., electronic patient portal)
mod_mismatch_context	Indication of whether there is a discrepancy between the intended and actual context of interface use	0 = no (i.e., the actual context of use matches the intended one) 1 = yes (i.e., the actual	Example for 0: educational game tested with children during teaching hours. Example for 1: driving simulator tested in a university setting.

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
			context of use does not match the intended one)
mod_perf_measure	Type of method the study participants' performance was measured with	0 = speed, 1 = accuracy, 2 = efficiency, 3 = learning output, 4 = depth of interaction, 5 = other measurement	Speed: e.g., task completion time, response time, number of tasks completed during a set time Accuracy: e.g., number of errors, number of correct answers Efficiency: e.g., number of clicks/commands needed, number of help requests Learning output: e.g., quantity and quality of information recalled Depth of interaction: e.g. dwell time, site penetration Other measurement: e.g. creativity
direction_within_each_measure	Meaning of measurement direction	1 = the higher, the better, -1 = the lower, the better	Example for performance measure "accuracy:" number of correct answers indicated by 1 (i.e., the more the better) and number of errors indicated by -1 (i.e., the less the better).
mod_confounders	Control of confounding variables	0 = not controlled, 1 = controlled for	Experienced usability reflects the study participants' subjective evaluation of usability during or after using the interface (Lee & Koubek, 2012).

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
		experienced usability when using the interface, 2 = controlled for multiple variables, including experienced usability	Confounding objective performance indicators (as assessed in this meta-analysis) with one's subjective perception of performance is likely to influence the nature of findings (e.g., Ben-Bassat et al., 2006; Lavie et al., 2011; Sonderegger, Uebelbacher, et al., 2014).
mod_usability	Level of the interface's inherent usability	0 = good, 1 = poor	Inherent usability comprises the interface's objective characteristics (Kurosu & Kashimura, 1995) based on which the participants could effectively and efficiently interact with the interface (e.g., the interface's response time, baseline number of keystrokes to complete a task). Good usability: no limitations on effectiveness and efficiency. Poor usability: limitations on effectiveness and efficiency.
Study design			
setting_type	Type of experimental setting	0 = in person setting, 1 = online setting,	In person setting: experiment conducted in a lab setting.

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
		2 = mix of both settings	Online setting: experiment conducted online. Mix of both settings: experiment conducted both in a lab setting and online.
design_type	Type of study design	0 = between-subjects, 1 = within-subjects	Between-subjects design: each participant completed one experimental condition (high aesthetics or low aesthetics). Within-subjects design: each participant completed both experimental conditions (high aesthetics and low aesthetics).
aesth_conditions	Indication of whether the aesthetic conditions are defined a priori or a posteriori	0 = a priori definition of conditions, 1 = a posteriori definition of conditions	A priori definition of conditions: aesthetics as an independent variable, manipulated a priori in the sense of a high vs. low aesthetic condition. Note that aesthetics could also be measured as one of the dependent variables in these studies. A posteriori definition of conditions: aesthetics as one of the dependent variables, differing significantly between observed variants of the interface so that a high vs. low aesthetic condition can be formed a posteriori.
n_aesth_high	Sample size of the aesthetically appealing condition	[Figure]	In case of a between-subjects design, sample sizes of the experimental conditions could differ.

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
n_aesth_low	Sample size of the aesthetically unappealing condition	[Figure]	
mean_aesth_high	Mean of performance in the aesthetically appealing condition	[Figure]	
mean_aesth_low	Mean of performance in the aesthetically unappealing condition	[Figure]	
sd_aesth_high	Standard deviation of performance in the aesthetically appealing condition	[Figure]	
sd_aesth_low	Standard deviation of performance in the aesthetically unappealing condition	[Figure]	
Effect sizes			
d	Effect size Cohen's d	[Figure]	
d_var	Variance of Cohen's d	[Figure]	
J	Hedge's factor J to correct for the bias of Cohen's d : $J = 1 - 3 / (4 * (n_aesth_high + n_aesth_low - 2) - 1)$	[Figure]	Cohen's d tends to overestimate the effect size in small samples. Hedges' factor J corrects this bias (Borenstein et al., 2009).
g	Standardized mean difference Hedge's g ($g = d * J$)	[Figure]	
g_var	Variance of Hedge's g	[Figure]	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
how_calculated	Data with which the effect size Hedge's g is calculated	0 = calculation from raw data 1 = calculation from M , SD and N per condition 2 = calculation from correlation r 3 = calculation from F -test statistics or η^2 4 = calculation from Cohen's d	If the required effect size Hedge's g was not reported in the study, it needed to be calculated from the given information: For transforming the correlation r , the formula by Borenstein et al. (2009, p. 48) was used. For transforming η^2 a function developed by Jin (2021) based on Cohen (1988) was used. Note that Jin's (2021) formula is only valid in case of a within-subjects design and a numerator degree of freedom of 1 in an F -Test.
Quality assessment (Study DIAD; Valentine & Cooper, 2008)			
Construct validity			
diad_question1	Rating on the Study DIAD's global question on construct validity (i.e., fit between concepts and operations)	0 = yes, 1 = maybe yes, 2 = maybe no, 3 = no	The answer to this question was deduced from the answers to the questions 1.1 and 1.2 using the algorithm developed by Valentine & Cooper (2008).
diad_question1.1	Rating on Study DIAD's composite question 1.1 on the study's intervention: "Were the participants	0 = yes, 1 = maybe yes, 2 = maybe no,	The answer to this question was deduced from the

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	treated in a way that is consistent with the definition of the intervention?"	3 = no	answers to the questions 1.1.1 to 1.1.4 using the algorithm developed by Valentine & Cooper (2008).
diad_question1.1.1	Rating on Study DIAD's question 1.1.1 on the study's intervention: "To what extent does the intervention reflect commonly held or theoretically derived characteristics about what it should contain?"	0 = fully, 1 = largely, 2 = fully, largely, or somewhat, 3 = not at all	
diad_question1.1.2	Rating on Study DIAD's question 1.1.2 on the study's intervention: "Was the intervention described at a level of detail that would allow its replication by other implementers?"	0 = yes, 1 = no	
diad_question1.1.3	Rating on Study DIAD's question 1.1.3 on the study's intervention: "Was there evidence that the group receiving the intervention might also have experienced a changed expectancy, novelty, and/or disruption effect not also experienced	0 = no, 1 = yes	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	by the comparison group (or vice versa)?”		
diad_question1.1.4	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 1.1.4 on the study’s intervention: “Was there evidence that the intervention was implemented in a manner similar to the way it was defined?”	0 = yes, 1 = no	
diad_question1.2	Rating on Study DIAD’s composite question 1.2 on the study’s outcome measure: “Were the outcomes measured in a way that is consistent with the proposed effects of the intervention?”	0 = yes, 1 = maybe no, 2 = no	The answer to this question was deduced from the answers to the questions 1.2.1 to 1.2.3 using the algorithm developed by Valentine & Cooper (2008).
diad_question1.2.1	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 1.2.1 on the study’s outcome measure: “Do items on the outcome measure appear to represent the content of interest (i.e., have face validity)?”	0 = yes, 1 = no	
diad_question1.2.2	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 1.2.2	0 = yes, 1 = no	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	on the study's outcome measure: "Were the scores on the outcome measure acceptably reliable?"		
diad_question1.2.3	Rating on Study DIAD's question 1.2.3 on the study's outcome measure: "Was the outcome measure properly aligned to the intervention condition?"	0 = yes, 1 = proper, 2 = no	
Internal validity			
diad_question2	Rating on the Study DIAD's global question on internal validity (i.e., clarity of causal inference)	0 = yes, 1 = maybe yes, 2 = maybe no, 3 = no	The answer to this question was deduced from the answers to the questions 2.1 and 2.2 using the algorithm developed by Valentine & Cooper (2008).
diad_question2.1	Rating on Study DIAD's composite question 2.1 on fair comparison within the study: "Were the participants in the group receiving the intervention comparable to the participants in the comparison group?"	0 = yes, 1 = maybe yes, 2 = maybe no, 3 = no	The answer to this question was deduced from the answers to the questions 2.1.1 to 2.1.3 using the algorithm developed by Valentine & Cooper (2008).
diad_question2.1.1	Rating on Study DIAD's question 2.1.1	0 = yes,	If this question was answered with "no", question

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	on fair comparison within the study: “Was random assignment used to place participants into conditions?”	1 = no	2.1.1a needed to be answered.
diad_question2.1.1a	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 2.1.1a on fair comparison within the study: “For Quasi-experiments: Were adequate equating procedures used to recreate the selection model? For Regression Discontinuity Designs: Could all participants have received the intervention had the cutoff point been set differently?”	0 = n/a, 1 = yes, 2 = no	
diad_question2.1.2	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 2.1.2 on fair comparison within the study: “Was there differential attrition between intervention and comparison groups?”	0 = no, 1 = yes	
diad_question2.1.3	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 2.1.3 on fair comparison within the study: “Was there severe attrition overall?”	0 = no, 1 = yes	
diad_question2.2	Rating on Study DIAD’s composite	0 = yes,	The answer to this question was deduced from the

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	question 2.2 on lack of contamination within the study: “Was the study free of events that happened at the time as the intervention that confused the intervention’s effect?”	1 = maybe yes, 2 = no	answers to the questions 2.2.1 to 2.2.3 using the algorithm developed by Valentine & Cooper (2008).
diad_question2.2.1	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 2.2.1 on lack of contamination within the study: “Was there evidence of a local history event?”	0 = no, 1 = yes	
diad_question2.2.2a	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 2.2.2a on lack of contamination within the study: “Were the intervention and comparison groups drawn from the same local pool?”	0 = no, 1 = yes	
diad_question2.2.2b	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 2.2.2b on lack of contamination within the study: “If yes, were intervention conditions known to study participants, providers, data collectors, and/or other authorities	0 = n/a, 1 = no, 2 = yes	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	(e.g., parents, teachers, case managers)?”		
diad_question2.2.3	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 2.2.3 on lack of contamination within the study: “Did the description of the study give any other indication of the strong plausibility of other intervention contaminants?”	0 = no, 1 = yes	
External validity			
diad_question3	Rating on the Study DIAD’s global question on external validity (i.e., generality of findings)	0 = yes, 1 = maybe yes, 2 = maybe no, 3 = no	The answer to this question was deduced from the answers to the questions 3.1 and 3.2 using the algorithm developed by Valentine & Cooper (2008).
diad_question3.1	Rating on Study DIAD’s composite question 3.1 on inclusive sampling within the study: “Did the study include variation on participants, settings, outcomes, and occasions representative of the intended beneficiaries?”	0 = yes, 1 = maybe yes, 2 = maybe no, 3 = no	The answer to this question was deduced from the answers to the questions 3.1.1 to 3.1.6 using the algorithm developed by Valentine & Cooper (2008).
diad_question3.1.1	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 3.1.1	0 = yes,	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	on inclusive sampling within the study: “Did the sample contain participants with the necessary characteristics to be considered part of the target population?”	1 = no	
diad_question3.1.2	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 3.1.2 on inclusive sampling within the study: “To what extent did the sample capture variation among participants on important characteristics of the target population?”	0 = fully, 1 = reasonable range, 2 = limited	
diad_question3.1.3	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 3.1.3 on inclusive sampling within the study: “To what extent did the study include variation on important characteristics of the target setting?”	0 = fully, 1 = reasonable range, 2 = limited	
diad_question3.1.4	Rating on Study DIAD’s question 3.1.4 on inclusive sampling within the study: “To what extent were	0 = fully, 1 = reasonable range, 2 = limited	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	important classes of outcome measures included in the study?"		
diad_questions3.1.5	Rating on Study DIAD's question 3.1.5 on inclusive sampling within the study: "Did the study measure the outcome at a time appropriate for capturing the intervention's effect?"	0 = yes, 1 = no	
diad_questions3.1.6	Rating on Study DIAD's question 3.1.6 on inclusive sampling within the study: "Was the study conducted during the time frame appropriate for extrapolating to current conditions?"	0 = yes, 1 = no	
diad_question3.2	Rating on Study DIAD's composite question 3.2 on effects tested within subgroups in the study: "Was the intervention tested for its effect within important subgroups of participants, settings, and outcomes?"	0 = yes, 1 = maybe yes, 2 = maybe no, 3 = no	The answer to this question was deduced from the answers to the questions 3.2.1 to 3.2.4 using the algorithm developed by Valentine & Cooper (2008).
diad_question3.2.1	Rating on Study DIAD's question 3.2.1	0 = fully, 1 = reasonable range,	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
diad_question3.2.2	<p>on effects tested within subgroups in the study: “To what extent was the intervention tested for effectiveness within important subgroups of participants?”</p> <p>Rating on Study DIAD’s question 3.2.2</p>	<p>2 = somewhat, 3 = not at all</p>	
diad_question3.2.3	<p>on effects tested within subgroups in the study: “To what extent was the intervention tested for effectiveness within important subgroups of settings?”</p> <p>Rating on Study DIAD’s question 3.2.3</p>	<p>0 = fully, 1 = reasonable range, 2 = somewhat, 3 = not at all</p>	
diad_question3.2.4	<p>on effects tested within subgroups in the study: “Was the intervention tested for its effectiveness across important classes of outcomes?”</p> <p>Rating on Study DIAD’s question 3.2.4</p> <p>on effects tested within subgroups in the study: “Was the time of measurement (relative to the end of the intervention) tested as an</p>	<p>0 = yes, 1 = no</p> <p>0 = yes, 1 = no</p>	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	influence on the intervention's effect?"		
Statistical validity			
diad_question4	Rating on the Study DIAD's global question on statistical validity (i.e., precision of outcomes)	0 = yes, 1 = maybe yes, 2 = maybe no, 3 = no	The answer to this question was deduced from the answers to the questions 4.1 and 4.2 using the algorithm developed by Valentine & Cooper (2008).
diad_question4.1	Rating on Study DIAD's composite question 4.1 on the study's effect sizes and standard errors: "Were effect sizes and their standard errors accurately estimated?"	0 = yes, 1 = maybe yes, 2 = maybe no, 3 = no	The answer to this question was deduced from the answers to the questions 4.1.1 to 4.1.4 using the algorithm developed by Valentine & Cooper (2008).
diad_question4.1.1	Rating on Study DIAD's question 4.1.1 on the study's effect sizes and standard errors: "Was the assumption of independence met, or could dependence (including dependence arising from clustering) be accounted for in estimates of effect sizes and their standard errors?"	0 = yes, 1 = no	
diad_question4.1.2	Rating on Study DIAD's question 4.1.2	0 = yes,	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	on the study's effect sizes and standard errors: "Did the statistical properties of the data (e.g., distributional and variance assumptions, if any, presence of outliers) allow for valid estimates of the effect sizes?"	1 = no	
diad_question4.1.3	Rating on Study DIAD's question 4.1.3 on the study's effect sizes and standard errors: "Were the sample sizes adequate to provide sufficiently precise estimates of effect sizes?"	0 = yes, 1 = no	
diad_question4.1.4	Rating on Study DIAD's question 4.1.4 on the study's effect sizes and standard errors: "Were the outcome measures sufficiently reliable to allow adequately precise estimates of the effect sizes?"	0 = yes, 1 = no	
diad_question4.2	Rating on Study DIAD's composite	0 = yes, 1 = maybe yes, 2 = maybe no,	The answer to this question was deduced from the

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	question 4.2 on the study's effect sizes and standard errors: "Were the statistical tests adequately reported?"	3 = no	answers to the questions 4.2.1 to 4.2.4b using the algorithm developed by Valentine & Cooper (2008).
diad_question4.2.1	Rating on Study DIAD's question 4.2.1 on the study's effect sizes and standard errors: "To what extent were sample sizes reported (or estimable) from statistical information presented?"	0 = fully, 1 = largely, 2 = rarely	
diad_question4.2.2	Rating on Study DIAD's question 4.2.2 on the study's effect sizes and standard errors: "To what extent could directions of effects be identified for important measured outcomes?"	0 = fully, 1 = largely, 2 = rarely	
diad_question4.2.3	Rating on Study DIAD's question 4.2.3 on the study's effect sizes and standard errors: "To what extent could effect sizes be estimated for important measured outcomes?"	0 = fully, 1 = largely, 2 = rarely	
diad_question4.2.4b	Rating on Study DIAD's question	0 = fully,	

Variable name	Description	Data format or categories	Explanation
	4.2.4b on the study's effect sizes and standard errors: "Could estimates of effect sizes be computed using a standard formula (or its algebraic equivalent)?"	1 = largely, 2 = rarely	

Note. The answer categories for the quality assessment questions were set in accordance with the evaluation algorithm in the Study Design and Implementation Assessment Device (Study DIAD; Valentine & Cooper, 2008).

B2. Contextual Questions to the Study Design and Implementation Assessment Device (Study DIAD; Valentine & Cooper, 2008)

Contextual question	Study DIAD section	Answer to questions for evaluating research on the aesthetics–performance relationship
1. What commonly shared and/or theoretically derived characteristics of the intervention should be present in its definition and implementation?	Fit between concepts—intervention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usage of an interactive interface. • Aesthetics’ definition in line with Moshagen & Thielsch (2010). • Successful manipulation of the interface’s visual aesthetics (e.g., color, layout). • At least two aesthetic conditions (high vs. low aesthetics) compared. • Visual aesthetics measured as independent variable (i.e., conditions formed a priori) and/or dependent variable (i.e., conditions formed a posteriori).
i. Which of these characteristics are necessary to define interventions that “fully,” “largely,” and “somewhat” reflect commonly shared and/or theoretically derived characteristics?		For “fully,” all four must be present. There will be no “largely” or “somewhat” studies.
ii. What variations in the intervention are important to examine as potential moderators of effect size?		<p>Interface</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of device/interface • Duration of interaction • General usability of interface <p>Usage context</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Actual and intended usage context (i.e., leisure, learning, work) <p>Task</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of task (i.e., free use, search task, use function) <p>Visual aesthetics</p>

Contextual question	Study DIAD section	Answer to questions for evaluating research on the aesthetics–performance relationship
<p>2. What important characteristics of the intervention would we need to know in order to reliably replicate it with different participants, in other settings, at other times?</p>	<p>External validity</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of aesthetic manipulation • Instrument/scale to measure aesthetics and its reliability • Procedure of aesthetic assessment (e.g., point of time, from memory vs. with screenshots/interface as memory aid) • Participants confronted with either a collectively rated (un)aesthetic interface, or an individually rated (un)aesthetic interface. • Effect sizes for differences between aesthetic conditions • Type of device/interface • Type of task • Type of aesthetic manipulation <p>For in person settings only:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experimental setting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Group vs. individual setting ○ Room lighting • Technical equipment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Peripheral devices used (e.g., mouse, keyboard) ○ Screen settings (e.g., resolution, saturation, brightness, contrast of colors) <p>For “yes,” the first three characteristics must be present. Studies conducted in person are also required to give information about the experimental setting and technical equipment used.</p>
<p>3. What are the important classes of</p>	<p>Fit between</p>	<p>User performance</p>

Contextual question	Study DIAD section	Answer to questions for evaluating research on the aesthetics–performance relationship
outcomes?	concepts— outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speed • Accuracy • Efficiency • Learning output • Depth of interaction
i. What classes of outcomes are needed to conclude that a reasonable range of operations and/or methods have been included and tested?		Any three classes of outcome for “fully.” Any two classes of outcome for “reasonable.” Any one class of outcome for “limited.”
4. Does the principal investigator have a minimum level of score reliability for outcomes to be considered in the review? If so, what are the specific minimum reliability coefficients for internal consistency, temporal stability, and/or inter-rater reliability (as appropriate)?	Fit between concepts— outcomes	No, a minimum level of reliability is not considered since the reliability of outcome measures is rarely given in the included studies. Instead, we indicated that reliability is critical when the outcome measures lacks clear assessment criteria (e.g., rating of text production tasks) or when achieving an appropriate level of accuracy is technically questionable (e.g., measuring reaction time in milliseconds in an online experiment).
5. Considering the context of this study, during what interval of time should it have been conducted to be relevant to current conditions?	External validity— sampling	2000–2024

Contextual question	Study DIAD section	Answer to questions for evaluating research on the aesthetics–performance relationship
6. Considering the context of this study, what are the characteristics of the intended beneficiaries of the intervention?	External validity—sampling	Interface users in different contexts (i.e., leisure, learning, work).
7. What are the important characteristics of participants that might be related to the intervention’s effect and must be equated if a study does not employ random assignment?	Causal inference—selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender • Age • Education level • Visual impairments (e.g., impaired color vision) • Experience with operating interfaces (e.g., usage of computers, surfing on the Internet)
8. What characteristics of subgroups of participants are important (a) to have variation on and (b) to test within a study to determine whether an intervention is effective within these groups? What levels or labels capture this variation?	External validity—effects tested within subgroups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender • Age • Education level • Visual impairments (e.g., impaired color vision) • Experience with operating interfaces (e.g., usage of computers, surfing on the Internet) • Other target groups who also use the interface (e.g., testing a university website with students and teachers).
i. Which of these characteristics of subgroups of participants are needed to conclude that a “limited” or “reasonable” range of characteristics		Any one characteristic for “limited.” Any three characteristics for “reasonable.” For “fully,” three characteristics must be present and (a) in the case of a context-specific interface, consider at least one other target group for the interface, or (b) in

Contextual question	Study DIAD section	Answer to questions for evaluating research on the aesthetics–performance relationship
have been included and tested?		the case of a widely used interface, capture variation in users through the sampling method.
<p>9. What characteristics of settings are important to test within a study to determine whether an intervention is effective within these groups?</p>	<p>External validity—effects tested within subgroups</p>	<p>In person setting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardized lab setting <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Group vs. individual setting ○ Time of day ○ Standardized room lighting • Technical equipment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Type of device used (e.g., computer, tablet, smartphone) ○ Peripheral devices used if applicable (e.g., mouse, keyboard) ○ Standardized screen settings (e.g., resolution, saturation, brightness, contrast of colors) • Actual usage context (i.e., leisure, learning, work) <p>Online setting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Type of device used (e.g., computer, tablet, smartphone) • Actual usage context (i.e., leisure, learning, work)
<p>i. Which of these characteristics and settings are needed to conclude that a “full”, “reasonable”, or “limited” range of variations have been tested?</p>		<p>In person setting</p> <p>For “fully,” the study must test variations on the following characteristics: group vs. individual setting, time of day, type of device used, actual usage context (if applicable to the interface). Two of these characteristics for “reasonable” and any one for “limited.”</p>

Contextual question	Study DIAD section	Answer to questions for evaluating research on the aesthetics–performance relationship
10. What is the appropriate interval for measuring the intervention’s effect relative to the end of the intervention?	External validity— inclusive sampling	<p>Online setting</p> <p>For “fully,” the study must test variations on both characteristics: type of device and actual usage context (if applicable to the interface). One of these characteristics for “reasonable” and none for “limited.”</p> <p>The interval depends on the interaction time with the interface (i.e., few seconds, few minutes to an hour, few hours/days/weeks). The intervention’s effect should be measured right after the interaction time has ended.</p>
11. Considering the context of this study, for purposes of sampling, what constitutes the local pool of participants?	Internal validity— lack of contamination	Participants drawn from the same environment/context (e.g., students attending the same course/university).
<p>If participants are drawn from the same local pool, which groups of individuals (e.g., students, teachers, parents, administrators, case workers) might have been able to interfere with the fidelity of the comparison group if they knew who was in the intervention and comparison groups?</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In person setting: study instructor, users in either group • In learning context (e.g., school, university): teachers
12. For research on this topic, how would you	Internal	More than a 10% difference in attrition percentages between groups.

Contextual question	Study DIAD section	Answer to questions for evaluating research on the aesthetics–performance relationship
define differential attrition from the intervention and control groups?	validity— selection	
13. For research on this topic, how would you define severe overall attrition?	Internal validity— selection	In person setting More than 20% loss of the original sample (Schulz & Grimes, 2002). Online setting More than 50% loss of the original sample (since a 30% loss is considered an average dropout rate in online studies, cf. Galesic, 2006).
14. For research on this topic, what constitutes a minimal sample size that would permit a sufficiently precise estimate of the effect size?	Statistical validity— effect size estimation	30 per group
15. What percentage of important statistical information (i.e., sample size, direction of effect, effect size) is needed for the results of this study to be “fully”, “largely”, and “rarely” reported?	Statistical validity— reporting	If full statistical results are known for all measured outcomes, results are “fully reported.” If full statistical results are known for 75%–99% of measured outcomes, results are “largely reported.” If full statistical results are known for less than 75% of measured outcomes, results are “rarely reported.”
16. Considering the outcome measure and the context of this research question, what constitutes “Over-alignment” and “Under-alignment” of the intervention and outcome?	Fit between concepts— outcome	There are no outcomes that are over-aligned to the intervention for this research question. If the aesthetic difference between the interfaces is too weak (i.e., not significant), then the outcomes are under-aligned to the intervention.

Note. Before applying the Study DIAD to human–computer interaction research, the contextual questions must be answered to ensure customization. These questions define the aspects to be evaluated through the Study DIAD items and establish criteria for determining what is considered adequate or inadequate (cf. Valentine & Cooper, 2008). The Study DIAD section column refers to the four validity scores assessed by the DIAD: Construct validity or “fit between concept and operations,” internal validity or “clarity of causal inference,” external validity or “generality of findings,” and statistical conclusion validity or “precision of outcome estimation” (Valentine & Cooper, 2008, p. 140).